

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF NUMERACY LEVELS BEFORE AND AFTER IMPLEMENTING PROJECT MATH O’CLOCK HABIT AT SAN BUENAVENTURA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to find out whether Project Math O’clock Habit help the Grade 5 pupils of San Buenaventura ES of Sto. Angel District for S.Y. 2024-2025 enhance their numeracy level. This employed quantitative pre-experimental research design with 86 respondents through total enumeration technique. To analyze the data, mean, standard deviation, and t-test was used. The findings revealed that before the implementation, only few respondents categorized as above average numerate while most fell under average numerate, emergent and non-numerate which is more than half of the population. After the intervention, the results improved significantly, with the majority reaching the above average numerate level and only a small number remaining in the lower categories. In addition, the average mean score results of the participants’ assessment in EGMA increased from 81.21 to 103.06 and the average MPS result from 64.24% to 82.50%. Lastly, there is also a significant difference between pre- and post-test scores of Grade 5 pupils after the implementation. Based on the statistical results, it shows that Project Math O’clock Habit was proven to be an effective program that helps to enhance numeracy level of Grade 5 pupils through increasing the abilities of pupils on the four fundamental operations in Mathematics. This recommends that the said project may be sustained and systematically implemented across other grade levels in the succeeding school years that will benefit the overall performance in Mathematics of the school. The positive result may also serve as a catalyst for stakeholders and policy makers to craft and conduct similar programs ensuring the enhancement of learners’ numeracy level.

Keywords: *EGMA, Mathematics, Math O’clock, numeracy level*

INTRODUCTION

Numeracy is described as the capacity to understand and use numbers in a variety of circumstances. It includes abilities including counting, number recognition, and fundamental arithmetic procedures. Early numeracy abilities are important because they predict future academic achievement in mathematics and other areas (Geary, 2014).

However, research indicates that many learners, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds, struggle with numeracy. For example, a systematic study found that early numeracy competences in low-achieving children frequently focus on fundamental facts and arithmetic skills, with many children failing to fulfill expected benchmarks (Dole & Geiger, 2020). This implies educational sectors need to conduct different interventions that will help learners to enhance their numeracy level. For interventions

to be effective, deficient numeracy skills must be identified early. Focused instruction and support can enhance early numeracy skills (Lee & Choi, 2020).

In the local context, using the Early Grade Mathematics Assessment (EGMA) as the standardized assessment tool utilized in public schools to evaluate and monitor learners' numeracy levels (DO 57, s. 2015), results show concerns regarding the low numeracy level among pupils of San Buenaventura Elementary School have surfaced in recent years which was proven by assessment conducted every beginning of school year (**71.16% in 2022-2023, 69.09%-2023-2024, and 65.11% in 2024-2025 of the total enrolment falls under average numerate, emergent, and non-numerate**). Therefore, the primary issue and concern is to improve the quality of mathematics instruction and to assist the pupils in enhancing their numeracy level (Clements & Sarama, 2019).

To address this issue, **Project Math O'clock Habit** was established and implemented. As cited by Ramjan et al. (2014) programs that focus on foundational numeracy skills through engaging activities have shown positive results in improving numeracy among low-achieving students. Project Math O'clock Habit is an intervention program that utilize proponent's self-constructed activity sheets. The said activity sheets focused on enhancing the pupil's ability to solve simple mathematical equations using the four fundamental operations.

Although previous studies have shown that targeted instruction and engaging activities can improve early numeracy skills, limited studies have explored structured habit-forming interventions that regularly engage learners in practicing the four fundamental operations, particularly in the context of public elementary schools (OECD, 2020; World Bank, 2021). Moreover, there is a need to examine how consistent numeracy practice through school-based initiatives can support learners who fall under average numerate, emergent and non-numerate levels.

Thus, this research aims to find out whether Project Math O'clock Habit helps the Grade 5 pupils of San Buenaventura ES of Sto. Angel District for S.Y. 2024-2025 to enhance their numeracy level. This study was essential since its objective is to enhance pupils' numeracy level through increasing their abilities on the four fundamental operations in Mathematics. In addition, it supports the MATATAG Agenda of the Department of Education wherein one of the four critical components is to TAKE steps to accelerate the delivery of basic education services and provision of facilities; as well as the school implementation program of San Buenaventura ES, the E-SBES which is the S stands for Students' skills in literacy and numeracy to attain learning standards.

Specifically, the study seeks answers to the following:

1. What is the numeracy level of Grade 5 learners before the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit?
2. What is the numeracy level of Grade 5 learners after the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit?
3. What are the mean percentage scores of pre-test and post-test assessments?

4. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the Grades 5 pupils after implementing Project Math O'clock Habit?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a quantitative pre-experimental research design, specifically a one-group pretest–posttest design. The Project Math O'clock Habit was implemented among the learners, and their Early Grade Mathematics Assessment (EGMA) pre-test and post-test scores were compared to determine the effectiveness of the intervention.

This is participated by 86 enrolled Grade 5 pupils through total enumeration technique where all the participants are the total number of Grade 5 pupils enrolled in San Buenaventura Elementary School in Sto. Angel District, Division of San Pablo City for school year 2024-2025.

The data were gathered using the proponent's crafted activity sheets entitled "Math O'clock Habit Activity Sheets" which undergone with assessment and validation from the researcher's school Learning Resource coordinator, master teacher and school head. The said material was also quality assured by the Division Quality Assurance Team through Curriculum Implementation Division- Learning Resource Management Section (CID-LRMS) of the Division of San Pablo City. In addition, the Early Grade Mathematics Assessment (EGMA) tool was used to monitor the progress and analyzation of the comparison if there is significant difference between the results before and after the project implementation.

The study followed a structured procedure through the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit, an intervention program designed to enhance the numeracy level of Grade 5 learners, particularly in the four fundamental operations. First, a pre-assessment was conducted using the EGMA tool to determine the learners' initial numeracy level. Second, the intervention was implemented through the use of activity sheets developed by the proponent. Each activity sheet consisted of five items focusing on the four fundamental operations. These were answered daily from the fifth week of the second quarter until the fourth quarter of the School Year 2024–2025, scheduled from 12:00 p.m. to 12:30 p.m. The activity sheets were validated by experts prior to implementation. Third, weekly monitoring was conducted to track the learners' progress throughout the intervention period. Fourth, a post-assessment using the same EGMA tool was administered to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention. Lastly, a follow-up study entitled "Exploring Students' Perspectives on the Utilization of Math O'clock Habit Activity Sheets for Numeracy Level Enhancement" was conducted to assess the effectiveness of the developed instructional materials for improvement and dissemination purposes.

This study employed a quantitative method in analyzing data, which involves numerical, countable, and measurable variables. The collected data were tabulated and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. To describe the learners' numeracy level before and after the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit, as well as the mean percentage scores of the pre-test and post-test assessments, descriptive

statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used. To determine whether there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the Grade 5 learners after the implementation of the intervention, inferential statistics, specifically the paired t-test, was utilized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Numeracy Level of Grade 5 learners before the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit

Numeracy Level	Frequency	Percentage
Above Average Numerate	30	34.89%
Average Numerate	15	17.44%
Emergent	23	26.74%
Non-Numerate	18	20.93%
Total	86	100 %

Table 1 shows the numeracy level of Grade 5 learners before the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit. The data reveal a heterogeneous distribution of numeracy levels among Grade 5 learners prior to the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit. While a notable proportion of learners (34.89%) are classified as Above Average Numerate, this is contrasted by a substantial percentage of learners who fall within the lower proficiency levels specifically, 26.74% categorized as Emergent and 20.93% as Non-Numerate. Combined, these groups account for nearly half of the population (47.67%), indicating a significant presence of learners who lack mastery of foundational numeracy skills.

In addition, this disparity suggests that although some learners demonstrate strong mathematical competence, a considerable portion remains at risk of underachievement, particularly in performing the four fundamental operations. The relatively low percentage of learners in the Average Numerate category (17.44%) further implies a polarized distribution, where learners tend to cluster at either higher or lower ends of proficiency rather than in the middle range.

Therefore, the data implies that before the implementation, only few respondents categorized as above average numerate while most fell under average numerate, emergent and non-numerate which is more than half of the population.

In general, the table underscores the need for an intentional, school-based numeracy intervention, as a significant proportion of learners require additional support to achieve proficiency. This baseline condition provides a strong justification for the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit as a strategic response to address these learning disparities. According to OECD (2020), numeracy skills are foundational for cognitive development in children. Conducting interventions can significantly improve mathematical understanding and reasoning, which are critical for later academic success.

Table 2

Numeracy Level of Grade 5 learners after the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit

Numeracy Level	Frequency	Percentage
Above Average Numerate	53	61.63%
Average Numerate	22	25.58%
Emergent	9	10.46%
Non-Numerate	2	2.33%
Total	86	100 %

This table shows the numeracy level of grade five learners after the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit. This is based on the EGMA post-assessment test conducted on the end of the school year. The data indicate a substantial improvement in the numeracy levels of Grade 5 learners following the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit. A majority of learners (61.63%) are now classified as Above Average Numerate, representing a marked increase compared to the pre-implementation distribution. This shift suggests that the intervention was highly effective in elevating learners' proficiency in the four fundamental operations.

Additionally, the proportion of learners in the Average Numerate category rose to 25.58%, further indicating a positive upward movement in overall performance. In contrast, the percentages of learners in the lower proficiency levels significantly decreased, with only 10.46% categorized as Emergent and a minimal 2.33% as Non-Numerate. This reduction reflects the program's success in addressing foundational learning gaps and supporting struggling learners.

Based on the given data, the redistribution of learners from lower to higher numeracy levels demonstrates the effectiveness of structured, consistent, and time-based mathematical practice. It only implies that after the intervention, the results improved significantly, with the majority reaching the above average numerate level and only a small number remaining in the lower categories. Moreover, the decline in the number of non-numerate learners highlights the intervention's role in promoting inclusive learning, ensuring that even those at risk of underachievement are given opportunities to improve. This aligns with the principle that early and sustained numeracy support is critical in preventing long-term academic difficulties in mathematics.

To sum it up, conducting intervention like Project Math O'clock can help learners in enhancing their numeracy level. The significant increase in higher-level proficiency and the corresponding decrease in low-level performance underscore the value of integrating structured numeracy interventions into daily instructional practices. As supported by Luna (2023), a school-based intervention in numeracy among learners led significant increase in their numeracy level from non-numerate to higher proficiency.

Table 3
Mean Percentage Scores of Pre-test and Post-test Assessments

Name of Section	Mean		SD		MPS	
	Pre-test	Post-test	Pre-test	Post-test	Pre-test	Post-test
Grade 5- Melon	102.52	117.69	14.82	4.80	82.01%	94.32%
Grade 5-Pinya	86.68	104.37	20.50	8.55	69.34%	83.49%
Grade 5-Rambutan	54.44	87.12	26.76	22.17	41.38%	69.70%
Average	81.21	103.06	20.69	11.84	64.24%	82.50%

This table shows the mean percentage scores of pre and post-test assessments of the Grade 5 pupils on each section. The results show a consistent and substantial improvement in learners' performance following the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit.

Across all sections, the post-test mean scores increased markedly compared to the pre-test results. Grade 5–Melon improved from a mean of 102.52 to 117.69, Grade 5–Pinya from 86.68 to 104.37, and Grade 5–Rambutan from 54.44 to 87.12. This upward trend is further reflected in the overall average mean, which rose from 81.21 in the pre-test to 103.06 in the post-test, indicating a significant enhancement in learners' mathematical performance.

In terms of Mean Percentage Scores (MPS), all sections demonstrated notable gains. Grade 5–Melon increased from 82.01% to 94.32%, Grade 5–Pinya from 69.34% to 83.49%, and Grade 5–Rambutan from 41.38% to 69.70%. The overall MPS improved from 64.24% to 82.50%, suggesting that learners moved from a developing level of mastery toward a more proficient level after the intervention. Notably, Grade 5–Rambutan, which had the lowest pre-test performance, exhibited the most substantial improvement, indicating that the intervention was particularly effective for learners with initially low numeracy skills.

Furthermore, the standard deviation values decreased across all sections in the post-test (from an average of 20.69 to 11.84), suggesting a reduction in score variability among learners. This implies that learners' performance became more consistent after the intervention, reflecting a more uniform level of understanding across the group.

These findings support the effectiveness of structured and consistent numeracy interventions in improving both individual and group performance. The increase in mean scores and MPS, coupled with the decrease in variability, indicates not only improved achievement but also a narrowing of learning gaps among learners.

Generally, the data provide strong empirical evidence that Project Math O'clock Habit contributed to significant improvements in learners' numeracy performance, reinforcing its value as an effective instructional strategy. This aligns with educational research which emphasizes that targeted instructional interventions and regular practice can significantly enhance mathematical proficiency and promote equitable learning outcomes. As cited by Gaspar et al. (2015), interventions in numeracy skills are critical for developing mathematical competence and confidence, which leads to better educational and life outcomes for students.

Table 4

Test of Difference in the Pre-test and Post-test Scores in EGMA of Grade 5 Pupils after the Implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit

Pre-test		Post-test		t	Sig (2-tailed)	Remarks
Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
81.21	20.69	103.06	11.84	8.5373	<0.001	Significant

The results in Table 4 clearly indicate a statistically significant improvement in the mathematics performance of Grade 5 pupils after the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit. The mean score increased substantially from 81.21 (pre-test) to 103.06 (post-test), reflecting a notable gain in learners' mastery of the assessed competencies. At the same time, the standard deviation decreased from 20.69 to 11.84, suggesting that students' scores became more consistent after the intervention. This implies not only overall improvement but also a reduction in performance gaps among learners, which is a key indicator of effective instructional intervention.

The computed t-value of 8.5373 with a p-value < 0.001 strongly confirms that the observed difference is not due to chance. This level of significance provides robust evidence that Project Math O'clock Habit had a meaningful impact on learners' achievement. In educational research, such a high t-value typically reflects a large effect size, indicating that the intervention was not only statistically significant but also practically important in improving student outcomes.

Overall, the data provide compelling evidence that Project Math O'clock Habit is an effective intervention for enhancing numeracy level among Grade 5 pupils. The significant increase in mean scores, coupled with reduced variability and strong statistical support, underscores its potential as a sustainable strategy for improving both performance and equity in mathematics education. As cited by Mononen et al. (2014) mathematics interventions dramatically enhance pupils' numeracy skills, especially among those who are at risk of falling behind. These programs frequently incorporate systematic education, practice, and feedback.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were formulated:

1. **Baseline numeracy levels revealed significant learning gaps.** Prior to the implementation of Project Math O'clock Habit, more than half of the Grade 5 learners (65.11%) were classified as average numerate, emergent and non-numerate, indicating weak mastery of foundational mathematical skills and a high risk of underachievement.
2. **The intervention led to a substantial improvement in numeracy levels.** After implementation, the majority of learners (61.63%) progressed to the above average numerate category, while the proportion of low-performing learners drastically decreased, demonstrating the program's effectiveness in elevating learners' competencies.

3. **The improvement in performance is statistically significant.** The computed t-value (8.5373) and p-value (<0.001) confirm that the difference between pre-test and post-test scores is highly significant and not due to chance.
4. **Project Math O'clock Habit is an effective and sustainable intervention.** Overall, the findings demonstrate that structured, consistent, and time-based numeracy practices can significantly enhance mathematical proficiency, improve learning outcomes, and promote equity in mathematics education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light on the conclusions of the study, it is recommended that Project Math O'clock Habit may be sustained and systematically implemented across other grade levels in the succeeding school years. School administrators and teachers may consider institutionalizing the program as part of regular instructional practice to ensure continuous numeracy development.

Additionally, stakeholders and policymakers are encouraged to utilize the positive outcomes of this study as a basis for designing and supporting similar data-driven interventions aimed at improving learners' numeracy level. Future implementations may also include regular monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to further validate effectiveness and guide program refinement.

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